

THE USE OF MULTIMEDIA TOOLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH AND THEIR IMPACT ON HUMAN MENTAL ACTIVITY

Ibadullayev Firdavs Furkatovich

Assistant teacher of the Department of English Language Theory and Practice of the Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

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ANNOTATION

Been scientifically substantiated above that the means of creating opportunities for multimedia in the educational process are of great importance in the formation of modern approaches to the teaching of literature today. One of the multimedia tools is animation (Latin animatix), which means "animating" images using machine graphics. ¹The direct movement of "animated" images in front of the reader is striking. It attracts attention. It enters the human mind through various sensory organs. Computer animation is the synthesis of dynamic images on a computer. ²Man begins to understand the world through images. Whether it is dynamic or stationary, the human mind seals the appearance of the mouth. In the chain of contemplation, all other information related to that concept forms a loop. Therefore, in the course of the lesson the student understands the essence of the topic, with all the elements around it, there is a high demand for modern software teaching aids, as well as multimedia tools. Modern software training tools are

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Multimedia. It allows you to work with programs equipped with animation, sound, video. When multimedia is used, it affects various human senses. It is known that a person ³receives information through the sensory organs. If multimedia tools are used in the educational process, a doubly robust database is formed in the minds of children, which is formed both by sight and hearing. Without deviating from the main idea of the work being taught in the lesson, they serve as aids in explaining the essence of the fairy tale, story, novel to the teacher. The analysis that the author intends to convey should be taken as a basis by the teacher to go through the students' personal interpretations. The video information or animation that is received along with the teacher's comments activates the students' attention. Education becomes fun and emotional, and students experience aesthetic satisfaction. ⁴

Multimedia tools on the quality of the educational process through Gardner's teaching. In 1983, Howard Gardner put forward his famous theory. According to him, people will have not one single intellect, but many intellects, a set of mental abilities. ⁵In some of its features,

¹Tadjiev M., Ziyamuhamedov B., Uralova M., Designing lessons on pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. - Tashkent, 2012, B.204.

²Choriyev G., Software for three-dimensional imaging. - Tashkent, 2014.

³Tadjiev M., Ziyamuhamedov B., Uralova M., Designing lessons on pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. - Tashkent, 2012, B.204.

⁴Tadjiev M., Ziyamuhamedov B., Uralova M., Designing lessons on pedagogical technology and pedagogical skills. - Tashkent, 2012, B.204.

⁵Rakhmonov Sh., Learn to learn, rediscover perfect memory or brain abilities. - Tashkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2014, P.262.

this concept creates harmony with the sensory organs of man. That is, these mental abilities are formed in the core of the sensory organs. Gardner points out that we have eight intellects. They are musical-rhythmic, visual-visual, linguistic-verbal, mathematical-logical, kinesthetic-physical, interpersonal, personal and natural. ⁶Multimedia tools in general affect almost all of these types of intelligence . Below is a discussion of their impact on the development of reader, human takafuri.

Influence of educational multimedia tools on rhythmic intelligence .

In music-rhythm you can sing well, play an instrument, hear perfectly perfectly, feel the rhythm, learn well by listening to lectures, but you will be a great composer, you have this ability stronger than any other intellect. ⁷Some people have a high level of hearing development. The important aspect is not in the height of the hearing, but in the power of the tasks it can perform. The central nervous system receives information about all the processes that take place in the external and internal environment. This information is received through the sensory organs. Each sensory organ provides perception of only a certain type of effect. For example, the eye is affected by light and the ear by sound. ⁸It takes place through the fragmentation of much of the information that a person receives from the outside world throughout his life. And the information generated in this way is much more complete than the information received by other sensory organs. Humans receive sound waves from the environment through their hearing organs. Through hearing, a person learns speech and interacts. ⁹The inclusion of audio materials in multimedia and the placement of audio information in videos created with the help of animated films, as well as audio materials that can be placed in presentations, provide a clear reflection of the topic in the mind of the reader. That is, they receive sound waves. Through the audio, musical information placed on the animated board, the impact on this mental ability of the student is realized. The child, who has a strong intellect , remembers all the information on the subject and the concepts around it with the help of attached audio materials. The information he hears always reminds him of the essence of the subject. Let's say a student doesn't have this mental ability well developed. Gradually, using the methods used in the non-stop learning process, this ability begins to develop in him as well. As mentioned above, the child learns speech through this and is able to interact.

Influence of multimedia tools on visual-visual intelligence .

By seeing, we perceive objects and phenomena around us, observe their movement and change, and know their shape, color, size, and location. A person's reading, writing, drawing, watching, driving vehicles, acquiring knowledge, learning a trade, and all other activities are related to seeing. Almost 90% of the information a person receives from the outside world is received through the eyes. ¹⁰Visual-vision is the intellectual ability of the common man, characterized by the ability to imagine in the human brain, to see the big picture clearly, and

⁶Rakhmonov Sh., Learn to learn, rediscover perfect memory or brain abilities. - Tashkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2014, P.262.

⁷Rahmonov Sh. Learn to learn, rediscover perfect memory or your brain abilities. - Tashkent: New Age Valodi, 2014, P.262.

⁸Mavlonov O., Tilavov T., Aminov B. Biology (Man and his health). - Tashkent: "Teacher" Publishing House, 2019, B157.

⁹Mavlonov O., Tilavov T., Aminov B. Biology (Man and his health). - Tashkent: "Teacher" Publishing and Printing House, 2019, B165.

¹⁰Mavlonov O., Tilavov T., Aminov B. Biology (Man and his health). - Tashkent: "Teacher" Publishing House, 2019, B159.

engineers or painters are masters of brilliant imagination and fantasy. ¹¹In the activation of this process, the impact of animation technologies in particular is obvious. As animated films focus on "animating" graphics, the reader perceives it directly visually. In the methodology, this concept is also explained by the term "figurative memory". The essence of this term is that the child begins to learn creative thinking through "figurative memory" as a result of the influence of animated films on this type of intelligence. The visual mental ability in it lays the groundwork for another ability at its core - the ability to think creatively. The visualization technique is to form a descriptive image of the situations you want to happen. Visualization is considered very childish, because it uses the already very active imagination of children and directs it in a positive way. It doesn't matter if it's about taking an exam or making a new friend - this technique gives amazing results. Tasa vvur is very strong in children, so they take the idea of visualization lightly. ¹²Information received through the eye is stored in the human brain, both voluntarily and involuntarily. The use of illustrations, educational animations, videos in the classroom expands the visualization opportunities of students.

A number of new animated videos created by ATA Animation Studio to monitor the impact of animation technologies on the rhythmic and visual intelligence of music will be used in the educational process, namely in the 5th grade literature textbook on Bukhari and hadith.

Multimedia on linguistic-verbal intelligence.

Linguistic-verbal intelligence is characterized by the use of words, love of reading, knowledge of language, and mastery of speech, especially in debates, and is highly valued by lawyers or writers. ¹³Some people remember what they saw very well, which means that their memory is visual and does not understand the essence of the thing until they see it with their eyes. Others find it difficult to remember until they think for themselves, say their name, and imagine it in an abstract way. These are representatives of the word-logical memory type. ¹⁴The side-by-side transition of literature and mother tongue lessons is not in vain. In mother tongue classes, children are taught essay writing techniques. Basically, the student writes an essay on a literary-artistic topic. Essays on a creative and free subject, expressing the life and work of a writer or his impressions of a particular work in the field of literature, gradually form in the child a high level of verbal responsibility inherent in writers. The teacher who uses multimedia is required to include new words that are not present in the student's speech in the methods, teaching animation sheets, so that the word can be read to the child in full. 'the miner will have to post the speech. The combination of audio and video materials attached to these words simultaneously affects both visual-visual, musical-rhythmic, and linguistic-verbal intelligence.

Animated videos, presentations can also engage the child linguistically. Because in it, theoretical information and new words enter the reader's mind with the help of images and sounds. First, the learner develops an overview of the topic. Based on this imagination, the

¹¹Rahmonov Sh. Learn to learn, rediscover perfect memory or your brain abilities. - Tashkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2014, P.262.

¹²Kexo J., Fisher N. The power of the mind - in the service of children. - Tashkent: Davr Press, 2017, -B38,39.

¹³Rahmonov Sh. Learn to learn, rediscover perfect memory or your brain abilities. - Tashkent : Yangi asr avlodi , 2014, B .262.

¹⁴Karimova V., Umarov B., Akramova F. Psychology. - Tashkent, 2010. B64.

student learns to think logically, creatively, and critically. He enriches his written and oral speech with new words. At the same time, his interest in reading increases. In it, the ability to learn a new language is formed in conjunction with the ability to learn and memorize new words in the native language. He actively participates in various debates with his rich speech. Under the influence of multimedia tools on this mental ability, the student grows as a speech-competent person. In conclusion, it can be said that educational animation boards have a direct impact on this type of mental activity. This effect can be achieved through the above types of intelligence or some of the methods used in the educational process. In this case, the educator using educational multimedia tools will have to take into account that the methods he places on the board are fully compatible with this intellect.

Multimedia means on mathematical-logical intelligence .

Mathematical-logical intelligence is a powerful attribute of scientists, engineers and accountants, often related to analysis, problem solving, finding answers to scientific puzzles.¹⁵ Mathematical-logical intelligence is not only a calculation-oriented intelligence, but it also includes the analysis of scientific puzzles using logic, problem solving, finding alternative solutions to them. In some children, this ability is very strongly developed. Their inclination to this intellect is the basis of memory. Such students are able to quickly receive signals from abroad in this area. Case studies placed on various forms of multimedia tools help in the development of this type of intelligence. Educational situation - case study a method of teaching learners to find a solution to a purposeful situation. ¹⁶A case study, prepared for students on the topic, is a reflection of problem situations on educational animation boards and in the process of finding solutions to these problem situations in groups, a new mental ability begins to develop in the child's mind. That is, a mathematical-logical intellect is formed, or this type of mental ability helps in solving case studies.

It is also clear from the above considerations that educational animated videos have an indirect rather than a direct effect on the mathematical-logical intellect that is formed or existing in the circle of the child's thinking. In this process, various methods, such as growing, moving diagrams, tables (explained in the case study case) consisting of "animated" graphs, act as a tool.

Influence of multimedia means on kinesthetic-body intelligence.

Kinesthetic-body intelligence is the ability to understand the body well, to control one's body, to do a lot of hand-foot movements, dancers and sportsmen are clear examples. Some footballists may have achieved incredible kinesthetic-body intelligence, but he may fail math tests, yet his talent will be preserved.¹⁷

At first glance, this ability does not even seem to be a mental ability, and the impact of multimedia tools on this intelligence does not seem to exist at all. But, as mentioned above, animated films, which are an integral part of multimedia, are dynamic - "animated", or more precisely, a collection of moving images. Therefore, if an animated film based on somekind of themes and in the 5th grade literature textbook is prepared, and in the next lesson students

¹⁵Rahmonov Sh. Learn to learn, rediscover perfect memory or your brain abilities. - Tashkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2014, P.262.

¹⁶Ishmukhamedov R., Abdukodirov A., Pardaeva A. Innovative technologies in education. - Tashkent, 2008.

¹⁷Rahmonov Sh. Learn to learn, rediscover perfect memory or your brain abilities. - Tashkent: Yangi asr avlodi, 2014, P.263.

are given the task to stage these works themselves, then kinesthetic-body intelligence can also be affected. Another point is that if we understand the organs of the body not only the organs that develop physical ability, but also the eyes and ears mentioned above, the problem becomes even clearer. It summarizes all the effects observed in the visual, musical-rhythmic, linguistic-verbal, mathematical-logical types. The visual intellect is the organ of the body, the musical-rhythmic intellect is the ear, the linguistic-verbal intellect is the tongue, and the mathematical-logical intellect is the hemispheres of the brain. It is important to keep in mind the presence of signals from the upper body to the brain. Hence, all the above proofs are gathered at one point. In addition, the "aesthetics" at the heart of the word kinesthetic is also associated with emotions, which again refers to the issues of emotional cognition, feeling on the subject of the senses.

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